

Names of botanical genera dedicated to genuine persons

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Abstract

The current review article deals with names of botanical genera derived from personal names of ingenuine people (eponyms). It is a sort of continuation of the article dealing with generic names inspired by mythology, and like it is part of the project: Linguistic structure of binomial botanical denominations. Based on Conspectus of the Bulgarian vascular flora, genera names dedicated to real people are alphabetically arranged and accompanied by a short biographical reference for the corresponding eponym. The main word-formative rules relating to the grammatical form of this type of genera names are analyzed, indicating the detected deviations from the established nomenclature norms. Several particular cases of genera names involving additional word-formative elements also are noted.

Keywords: Botanical genera; Eponyms; Word-formation

1. Introduction

The present article examines the structure and meaning of a particular type of generic names in binominal botanical denominations. It is a sort of continuation of the review "Names of botanical genera inspired by mythology" published in this journal [1] dealing with genus names dedicated to deities and mythological heroes. The focus here is on the denominations given in honor of genuine persons as an expression of recognition and gratitude for their contribution to botany and science in general. The research is based on the Conspectus of the Bulgarian vascular flora, Sofia, 2012 [2], and is a part of a larger project: Linguistic structure of binomial botanical denominations.

Following the rules established by ICBN (International Code of Botanical Nomenclature): The name of a genus is a noun in the nominative singular, or a word treated as such, and is written with an initial capital letter (see Art. 60.2). It may be taken from any source whatever, and may even be composed in an absolutely arbitrary manner, but it must not end in -virus (Division II, Chapter III, Section 3, Article 20,1) [3].

Generic names are presented according to the IPNI (International Plant Names Index) [4], which provides detailed nomenclatural information regarding the correct spelling, the author and first place, and date of publication for the scientific names of Vascular Plants, as well as the status of each denomination.

The genus names considered in this article are formed based on the names of real people. These names do not reflect specific characteristics or peculiarities of the particular genus but represent an act of appreciation for the achievements of the corresponding eponym.

The ICBN recommends not to dedicate genera to persons quite unconnected with botany or at least with natural science [3, Recommendation 20 A]. That is why the considered names usually relate to persons involved in medicine and natural sciences – physicians, naturalists, botanists, and keen plant collectors. Many of them possess rich collections of plants,

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minerals, and fossils. Others create or manage botanical gardens; participate in explorer expeditions; collect and describe new species. These people laid the foundations for the systematic study of nature and botany in particular with their efforts, research, and scientific treatises.

Much less are the genus names given in honor of a famous scholar (*Galilea* – to commemorate Galileo Galilei), or a historical person for whom there is literary evidence, that she used the particular plant (*Euphorbia* – for Euphorbus, a Greek physician of the king of Numidia Juba II; *Gentiana* – for Gentius, the last king of the Illyria; *Carlina* – probably for Charlemagne, etc.).

2. Names of genera

2.1 Aldrovanda

Aldrovanda L. Species Plantarum (1753)

Aldrovanda L. Genera Plantarum ed.5 (1754)

The genus name is dedicated to Ulisse Aldrovandi (in Italian is also called Aldroandi [6]), Latinized as Ulysses Aldrovandus (1522 – 1605). Italian physician and pharmacist, naturalist and botanist, professor of philosophy and natural sciences at the University of Bologna. Director of the public botanical garden in Bologna. Author of an "Historia naturalis" [5].

2.2 Ammannia

Ammannia L., Genera Plantarum ed.5 (1754)

Ammannia L., Sp. Pl. 1: 119 (1753)

The genus is named for Paul Ammann (1634 – 1691), a German physician and botanist, professor of botany, and director of the botanical garden at the University of Leipzig, author of "Supellex Botanica" (1675) and "Character Naturalis Plantarum" (1676) [5].

2.3 Andrzeiowskia

Andrzeiowskia Rchb., Iconogr. Bot. Pl. Crit. 1: 15, t. 15 (1823)

The genus name is dedicated to Antoni Lukianowicz Andrzejowski (1785 – 1868), a Polish-Lithuanian botanist and paleontologist, professor at Kyiv, member of the Moscow Society of naturalists and also the Warsaw Natural History Society, researcher of Ukraine flora, and director of the Stavyshe Botanical Garden in Ukraine [5].

2.4 Aubrieta

Aubrieta Adans., Fam. Pl. (Adanson) 2: 420 (1763)

The genus is dedicated to Claude Aubriet (1665 – 1742), a French botanical illustrator at the Jardin du Roi in Paris and a royal botanical painter from 1707. Aubriet accompanied Joseph Pitton de Tournefort and the German physician and botanist Andreas von Gundelsheime on their expedition to the Middle East from 1700 to 1702. His numerous drawings and nature history miniatures are kept in the Prints and Drawings Department of the National Library in Paris [6].

2.5 Bartsia

Bartsia L., Genera Plantarum ed.5 (1754)

Bartsia L., Sp. Pl. 2: 602 (1753) nom. cons.

The genus is dedicated to Johann Bartsch, Latinized as Bartsius (1709 – 1738), a German physician, keen botanist and plant collector, acquaintance and assistant of Linnaeus with the publication of "Flora Lapponica". By the solicitation of Linnaeus, Bartsch was sent to Suriname, where he died prematurely. In his honor, Linnaeus denominates the genus *Bartsia* after him [5].

2.6 **Bassia**

Bassia All., Mélanges Philos. Math. Soc. Roy. Turin 3: 177 (1766)

Bassia J. Koenig, Mant.Pl. Altera [Linnaeus] 555 (1771), nom. illeg.

The genus is dedicated to Ferdinando Bassi (1710 – 1774), an Italian naturalist and botanist, plant collector, prefect of the Bologna Botanical Garden, and author of "Ambrosina novum plantae genus" (1763). He was a correspondent of some scientists of his time, including Linnaeus [5].

2.7 **Beckmannia**

Beckmannia Host, Icon. Descr. Gram. Austriac. 3: 5, t. 6 (1805)

The genus is named for Johann Beckmann (1739 – 1811), a German scientist and traveler who taught Physics, Natural History, and Economics in Göttingen, where in 1768 founded a botanic garden on the principles of Linnaeus. The word "technology" is believed to be created by him [5].

2.8 **Bellardia**

Bellardia Schreb., Gen. Pl., ed. 8[a]. 2: 790 (1791), nom. illeg.

Bellardia All., Fl. Pedem. 1: 61 (1785)

The genus is dedicated to Carlo Antonio Lodovico Bellardi (1741 – 1826), an Italian physician, botanist, and mycologist, professor at the University of Turin, and author of a voluminous herbarium [6].

2.9 **Bellarrdiochloa**

Bellardiochloa Chiov., in Stud. Veg. Piemonte (II. Cent. Fondaz. Bot. Univ. Torino, 1729-1929) 60(1929)

The name is composed of Bellardi (see 2.8.) and the Greek *χλόα* (grass) [6].

2.10 **Bellevalia**

Bellevalia Lapeyr., J. Phys. Chim. Hist. Nat. Arts 67: 425 (1808)

Bellevalia Scop., Introd. Hist. Nat. 198 (1777)

The genus is named after Pierre Richer de Belleval (1564 – 1632), a French physician and botanist, professor of botany at Montpellier, and founder of the university's botanical garden of Montpellier – the first botanical garden in France [5].

2.11 **Berteroa**

Berteroa DC., Mém. Mus. Hist. Nat. 7:232 (1821)

The genus is dedicated to Carlo Luigi Giuseppe Bertero (1789 – 1831), a Piedmontese physician and botanist, and plant collector during expeditions in the islands of the Antilles as well as in South America. Particularly significant is the exploration of the island of Mas a Tierra in the Juan Fernández archipelago. Between 1828 and 1830, he explored the central regions of Chili, collecting huge collections. Died in the Pacific during a return voyage from Tahiti [6].

2.12 **Bilderdykia**

Bilderdykia Dumort., Fl. Belg. (Dumortier) 18 (1827)

The genus is dedicated to Willem Bilderdyk (or Bilderdijk) (1756 – 1831), a Dutch poet, writer, lawyer, and librarian to Louis-Napoleon, who made him a president of the Institute Royal de France [5].

2.13 **Blackstonia**

Blackstonia Huds., Fl. Angl. (Hudson) 146, nomen prius (1762)

The genus is named after John Blackstone (1712 – 1753), an English pharmacist and botanist, author of "Fasciculus plantarum circa Harefield sponte nascentium" (1737) and "Specimen botanicum" (1746), containing 367 British plants description [5, 6].

2.14 Broussonetia

Broussonetia Ortega, Nov. Rar. Pl. Descr. Dec. 61 (1798), nom. rej.

Broussonetia L'Hér. ex Vent., Tabl. Regn. Vég. 3: 547 (1799), nom. cons.

The genus is dedicated to Pierre Marie Auguste Marie Broussonet (1761 – 1807), a French politician, physician, and botanist who traveled in the Canary Islands, France, Morocco, and Portugal and was the first to import female plants of *Broussonetia papyrifera* from China at the end of the 18th century. Professor and director of the botanical garden at Montpellier. Author of several writings among which "Elenchus plantarum horti botanici Monspeliensis" (1805) [5, 6].

2.15 Bruckenthalia

Bruckenthalia Rchb., Fl. Germ. Excurs. 414 (1831)

The genus is dedicated to Baron Samuel von Bruckenthal (1721 – 1803), an Austrian nobleman, governor of Transylvania on behalf of the Habsburgs, and patron of science and botany [5, 7].

2.16 Caldesia

Caldesia Parl., Fl. Ital. (Parlatore) 3(2): 598 (1860)

The genus of mushrooms is dedicated to Lodovico Caldesi (1821 – 1884), an Italian botanist and mycologist from Faenza, active politician during the Risorgimento, and Member of Parliament. Author of "Florae Faventinae Tentamen". His herbarium is held in the Botanical Garden of the University of Bologna, and his library containing a set of botany and natural sciences works is at the Municipal Library in Faenza [6].

2.17 Carlina

Carlina L., Sp. Pl. 2: 828 (1753)

The etymology of the name is discussible. A late legend relates it to Charlemagne, Latinized as Carolus Magnus (747 – 814) who allegedly used it to treat his soldiers struck by the plague [6, 7]. Linnaeus attributed the name to King Charles V (Carlos I of Spain) (1500 – 1558) [5, 6].

2.18 Commelina

Commelina L., Sp. Pl. 1: 40 (1753)

The genus name is given in honor of Jan (Johannes) Commelin (1629 – 1692), a Dutch botanist, professor in Amsterdam, a scholar of the flora of Holland and the West Indies [6], director of the botanical garden, and of his nephew Caspar Commelin (1668 – 1731), physician and botanist, professor at the Collegium Medicum. According to Linnaeus each of them represents one of the amazing petals of *Commelina communis* [5].

2.19 Conringia

Conringia Heist. ex Fabr., Enum. [Fabr.], 160(1759)

The genus is dedicated to Hermann Conring (1606 – 1681), a German physician and naturalist with contributions to medicine, law, and politics. Author of "De origine juris Germanici" (1643) [5].

2.20 Cortusa

Cortusa L., Sp. Pl. 1: 144 (1753)

The genus is named for Giacomo Antonio Cortuso (1513 – 1603), an Italian botanist, prefect of the Padua Botanical Garden, author of "L'horto dei simplici di Padova" (1592) [5].

2.21 *Danthonia*

Danthonia DC., Fl. Franc. [de Candolle & Lamarck], ed. 3. 3:32 (1805)

The genus is dedicated to Étienne Danthoine (1739 – 1794), a French pharmacist and botanist from Marseille, and student of grasses in Provence [5, 7].

2.22 *Danthoniastrum*

Danthoniastrum (Holub) Holub, Folia Geobot. Phytotax. 5: 435 (1970)

The genus name derives from *Danthonia* (see 2.21.) through suffix *-astrum* that expresses incomplete resemblance with pejorative nuance.

2.23 *Deschampsia*

Deschampsia P.Beauv., Ess. Agrostogr. 91 (1812)

The genus is dedicated to Louis Auguste Deschamps (1765 – 1842), a French physician, naturalist, and botanist who participated in the French explorer Entrecasteaux expedition aboard "La Recherche", researcher of the flora of Java and Mexico [6].

2.24 *Descurainia*

Descurainia Webb & Berthel., Hist. Nat. Iles Canaries (Phytogr.). 3(2, 1): 72 (1836)

The genus is dedicated to François Descourain (1658 – 1740), a French pharmacist, physician, and botanist [5,6].

2.25 *Desmazeria*

Desmazeria Dumort., Commentat. Bot. (Dumort.) 26 (1822)

The genus is dedicated to Jean Baptiste Henri Joseph Desmazières (1786 – 1862), a French botanist, physician, and amateur mycologist, editor of the scientific journals "Annales des sciences naturelles" and the "Bulletin de la société des sciences de Lille", creator of the series "Plantes cryptogames du Nord de la France" and "Plantes cryptogames de France" [5]. His treatise on the genus *Mycoderma*, titled "Recherches microscopiques et physiologiques sur le genre *Mycoderma*" was published in 1827.

2.26 *Dittrichia*

Dittrichia Greuter, Exsicc. Genav. Conserv. Bot. Distrib. Fasc. 4: 71 (1973)

The genus is named after Manfred Dittrich (1934 – 2016), a German botanist, plant collector, and family Asteraceae specialist, director of the Berlin Botanical Garden [6].

2.27 *Duchesnea*

Duchesnea Sm., Trans. Linn. Soc. London 10(2): 372 (1811)

Duchesnea Focke, Nat. Pflanzenfam. [Engler & Prantl] iii. 3. (1888) 33

The genus is dedicated to Antoine Nicolas Duchesne (1747 – 1827), a French botanist and horticulturist, professor at Versailles, the first descriptor of strawberries, and author of "Histoire naturelle des Fraisiers (1766) and "Sur la formation des jardins" (1775) [5, 6].

2.28 *Euphorbia*

Euphorbia L., Sp. Pl. 1: 450 (1753)

The genus name probably is relating to *Euphorbus*, a Greek physician to the king of Numidia Juba II, who – according to Pliny – discovered the medicinal virtues of this plant. The name itself "euphorbus" derives from Greek *εὖ* (good) and *φέρβω* (nourish) or *φορβή* (nourishment), therefore "well-fed" [6, 7].

2.29 Fallopia

Fallopia Adans., Fam. Pl. (Adanson) 2: 274, 277 (1763)

Fallopia Lour., Fl. Cochinch. 1: 335 (1790)

The genus is named for Gabriele Fallopio, Latinized as Fallopius (1523 – 1562), an Italian physician, anatomist, and pharmacologist, professor at the University of Pisa as well as of Padua, and also superintendent of the botanical gardens there [5, 7].

2.30 Fibigia

Fibigia Medik., Pflanzeng. i. 90 (1792)

The genus is named after Johann Fibig (Fiebig) (1758 – 1792), a German physician and botanist, professor at Mainz [5].

2.31 Frankenia

Frankenia L., Genera plantarum ed. 5 (1754)

Frankenia L., Sp. Pl. 1: 331 (1753)

The genus is named after Johannes Franck (Frankenius) (1590 – 1661), a Swedish botanist, professor of anatomy, medicine, and botany at the University of Upsala, author of a "Speculum botanicum" (1659), and a colleague of Carl Linnaeus [5].

2.32 Gagea

Gagea Salisb., Ann. Bot. [König & Sims]. 2(3): 555 (1806)

The genus is dedicated to Sir Thomas Gage, 7th Baronet of Hengrave (1781 – 1820), an English botanist and plant collector of rare European plants, possessing various specimens in his herbarium [5, 6].

2.33 Galilea

Galilea Parl., Fl. Palerm. i. 297 (1845)

The name is given in honor of Galileo Galilei (1564 – 1642), a famous Italian physicist, philosopher, astronomer, and mathematician, father of modern science [6].

2.34 Galinsoga

Galinsoga Ruiz & Pav., Fl. Peruv. Prodr. 110, t. 24 (1794)

The genus is dedicated to Ignacio Mariano Martinez de Galinsoga (1766 – 1797), a Spanish physician, scientist, and botanist, director of the Royal Madrid Botanical Garden [5, 6].

2.35 Gaudinia

Gaudinia J. Gay, in Bull. Ferussac, xviii. (1829) 412, nom. illeg.

Gaudinia P. Beauv., Ess. Agrostogr. 95 (1812), partim. (1812)

The genus is named after François Aimé GottliebThéophile Philippe Gaudin (1766 – 1833), a Swiss protestant pastor in Nyon, botanist, professor, and author of a "Flora Helvetica" in seven volumes [5, 6].

2.36 Gentiana

Gentiana L., Sp. Pl. 1: 227 (1753)

Gentiana L., Genera Plantarum ed. 5 (1754)

The name, according to Pliny, is given in honor of Gentius (in Greek *Γέντιος* or *Γενθιος*), the last king of the Illyria (181 – 168 BC). He discovered the antimalarial properties of the roots of *Gentiana lutea* [6, 7].

2.37 **Gentianella**

Gentianella Moench, Methodus (Moench) 482 (1794)

The name derives from *Gentiana* (see 2.35.) and through suffix *-ella* is formed diminutive noun, meaning "small gentian".

2.38 **Gleditsia**

Gleditsia J. Clayton, Genera Plantarum ed. 5 (1754)

Gleditsia J. Clayton, Sp. Pl. 2: 1056 (1753)

The genus is named in honor of Johann Gottlieb Gleditsch, Latinized as Gleditsius (1714 – 1786), a German physician and botanist, professor of botany at the Collegium Medico-chirurgicum, and director of the Botanical Garden of Berlin [5, 7].

2.39 **Goodyera**

Goodyera R. Br., Hort. Kew., ed. 2 [W.T. Aiton] 5: 197 (1813)

The genus is dedicated by the Scottish botanist Robert Brown to John Goodyer (1592 – 1664), an English naturalist and plant collector considered a precursor of modern botany, translator of a Latin version of Dioscorides' work "De Materia Medica" and Theophrastus' "Historia Plantarum" [5].

2.40 **Haberlea**

Haberlea Friv., in Magyar Tud. Tars. Evkon. II. (1835) 249. t. 1

Haberlea Pohl ex Baker, Fl. Bras. (Martius) 6(2): 341 (1876)

The genus is dedicated to Karl Konstantin Christian Haberle (1764 – 1832), an Austrian naturalist, botanist, and plant collector, professor of botany at Pest (now part of Budapest in Hungary), and director of the botanical garden [5].

2.41 **Hainardia**

Hainardia Greuter, Boissiera xiii. 178 (1967) in adnot.

The genus is named for Pierre Hainard (1936), a Swiss botanist and ecologist from Geneva [6].

2.42 **Hornungia**

Hornungia Rchb., Deutschl. Fl. (H. G. L. Reuchenbach) 1: 33 (1837)

Hornungia Bernh., Flora 23(2): 392 (1840)

The genus is dedicated to Ernst Gottfried Hornung (1795 – 1862), a German naturalist and botanist [5].

2.43 **Hottonia**

Hottonia L., Sp. Pl. 1: 145 (1753)

The genus is named in honor of Petrus Houttuyn, (1648 – 1709), a Dutch physician and botanist, often cited as Peter Hotton, professor of medicine and botany in Leiden, supervisor of the University Botanical Garden, and author of "Thesaurus Phytologicus" (1738) [5].

2.44 **Huetia**

Huetia Boiss., Diagn. Pl. Orient. ser. 2, 2: 103 (1856)

The genus is dedicated to Alfred Huet du Pavillon (1829 – 1907), a researcher of Sicilian and Sardinian flora, and his brother Édouard Huet du Pavillon (1819 – 1908), both French botanists [6].

2.45 *Huperzia*

Huperzia Bernh., J. Bot. (Schrader) 1800(2): 126 (1801)

The genus is named after Johann Peter Huperz (1771 – 1816), a German physician and botanist, ferns researcher, and author of "Specimen inaugurale medico-botanicum de Filicum propagatione" (1798) [5].

2.46 *Imperata*

Imperata Cirillo, Pl. Rar. Neapol. 2: [xxvi] (1792)

The genus is named after Ferrante Imperato (1550 – 1625), an Italian pharmacist and botanist from Naples, owner of a rich collection of curiosities, including a herbarium, shells, fossils, clays, minerals, marble and gems, that seemed a natural history museum, and was exhibited at Palazzo Gravina in Naples. Author of "Dell'Historia Naturale" (1599) [5, 7].

2.47 *Jurinea*

Jurinea Cass., Bull. Sci. Soc. Philom. Paris 1821: 140 (1821)

The genus is dedicated to Louis Jurine (1751 – 1819), a Swiss physician, botanist, and zoologist, or to his son André Jurine (1780 – 1804), a naturalist and scholar of medicine and botany, author of "Recherches sur l'organisation des feuilles" (1802) [5, 7].

2.48 *Kerneria*

Kerneria Medik., Pflanzeng. 71 (1782)

Kerneria Willd., Sp. Pl., ed. 4 [Willdenow] 4(2): 947 (1806)

Kerneria Medik., Pfl.-Gatt. 77, 95 (1792)

Kerneria Schrank, Baier. Reise 50 (1786)

The genus is dedicated to Johann Simon von Kerner (1755 – 1830), a German botanist and botanical illustrator, professor of botany at Stuttgart [6, 7].

2.49 *Kickxia*

Kickxia Blume, Rumphia 4:25 (1849)

Kickxia Dumort., Fl. Belg. (Dumortier) 35 (1827) (1827)

The genus is named after Jean Kickx (1775 – 1831), a Belgian botanist and mineralogist, professor of botany, pharmacy, and mineralogy in Brussels, and author of "Flora Bruxellensis" (1812) [5, 6].

2.50 *Knautia*

Knautia L., Sp. Pl. 1: 101 (1753)

The genus is dedicated to the German physicians and botanists Christopher Knaut (1638 – 1694), author of "Enumeratio Plantarum Circa Halam Saxonum Et In Eius Vicinia" (1687), and his brother Christian Knaut (1656 – 1716), author of "Compendium botanicum sive methodus plantarum genuina" (1718) [5].

2.51 *Kobresia*

Kobresia Willd., Sp. Pl., ed. 4 [Willdenow] 4(1): 205 (1805)

The genus is dedicated to Joseph Paul von Cobres (1747 – 1823), an Austrian banker, naturalist, natural history collector, and amateur botanist [5].

2.52 *Kochia*

Kochia Roth, J. Bot. (Schrader) 1800(1): 307 (1801)

The genus is dedicated to Wilhelm Daniel Joseph Koch (1771 – 1849), a German physician and botanist, professor of botany and medicine at the University of Erlangen, and director of the botanical garden. A foreign member of the Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences from 1833. Author of "Synopsis Florae Germanicae et Helveticae" (1837) [5, 6].

2.53 *Koeleria*

Koeleria Pers., Syn. Pl. [Persoon] 1: 97 (1805)

The genus is named after Georg Ludwig Koeler (1765 – 1807), a German physician, pharmacist, botanist, professor in Mainz, and author of the work on the family Poaceae: "Descriptio Graminum in Gallia et Germania" (1802) [6].

2.54 *Koelreuteria*

Koelreuteria Medik., Bot. Beob. 1782 [Medikus] 1782: 22 (1782), nom. illeg.

Koelreuteria Laxm., Novi Comment. Acad. Sci. Imp. Petrop. 16: 561, t. 18 (1772)

The name is given in honor of Joseph Gottlieb Kölreuter (1733 – 1806), a German physician and botanist, member of the Imperial Academy of Sciences at St. Petersburg, professor of natural history at Karlsruhe for a short time, and director of the botanical garden at Baden. Kölreuter scientifically studied the phenomena of hybridization, creating hybrids of numerous species and following their development for several generations [6, 7].

2.55 *Lavatera*

Lavatera L., Genera Plantarum ed. 5 (1754)

Lavatera L., Sp. Pl. 2: 690 (1753)

The genus is named after the Lavater family, Swiss physicians, and naturalists in Zurich: Heinrich Lavater (1560 – 1623) and his sons Johann Heinrich Lavater (1611 – 1691) and Johann Jacob Lavater (1594 – 1636) [5].

2.56 *Leersia*

Leersia Sw., Prodr. [O. P. Swartz] 1, 21 (1788)

The genus is dedicated to Johann Georg Daniel Leers (1727 – 1774), a German pharmacist and botanist, a researcher of Germanic flora, and author of "Flora Herbornensis" [5, 6].

2.57 *Legousia*

Legousia Durande, Fl. Bourgogne 1: 37 (1782)

The genus is named after Bénigne Le Gouz de Gerland (1695 – 1774), a French scholar historian, patron of the arts, founder of the botanical garden of Dijon, and donator of the Dijon Academy [5, 6].

2.58 *Lerchenfeldia*

Lerchenfeldia Schur, Enum. Pl. Transsilv. 753 (1866)

The genus is dedicated to Joseph Radnitzky von Lerchenfeld (1753 – 1812), an Austrian-born cleric, educator, and botanist [7].

2.59 *Lindernia*

Lindernia All., Mélanges Philos. Math. Soc. Roy. Turin 3(1): 178, t. 5, fig. 1 (1766)

The genus is named after Franz Balthasar von Lindern (1682 – 1755), a German physician and botanist, professor at Strasbourg of botany, chemistry, and pharmacology, director of the botanical garden, and researcher of the flora of Alsace, author of "Hortus Alsaticus" (1747) [5].

2.60 *Listera*

Listera Adans., Fam. Pl. (Adanson) 2: 321. Cf. LISSERA, Steud. (1763)

Listera R. Br. in W. T. Aiton, Hort. Kew. Ed.2 [W. T. Aiton] 5: 201 (1813)

The genus is dedicated to Martin Lister (1639 – 1712), an English physician and naturalist, a fellow of the Royal Society. Author of many articles on natural history, his most significant works being "Historia animalium Angliae tres tractatus" (1678), "Historiae Conchyliorum" (1685), and "Conchyliorum Bivalvium" (1696) [5, 6].

2.61 *Lloydia*

Lloydia Salisb., Trans. Hort. Soc. London 1: 328 (1812), nom. inval.

Lloydia Delile, Index Seminum [Montpellier] 1844: [3] (1844)

Lloydia Salisb. ex Rchb., Fl. Germ. Excurs. 102 (1830), nom. cons.

The genus is dedicated to the Welsh naturalist Edward Lloyd (Lhuyd), Latinized as Eduardus Luidius (1660 – 1709), an Oxford linguist, naturalist, botanist, and geographer, Keeper of the Ashmolean Museum, author of "Archaeologia Britannica" (1707) [5, 7].

2.62 *Lonicera*

Lonicera L., Genera Plantarum ed. 5 (1754)

Lonicera Boehm., Def. Gen. Pl., ed. 3. 139; vide Dandy, Ind. Gen. Vasc. Pl. 1753-74 (Regn. Veg. 51) 61 (1967), non L. (176)

Lonicera L., Sp. Pl. 1: 173 (1753)

Lonicera Gaertn., Fruct. Sem. Pl. 1: 132 (1788)

Lonicera Adans., Fam. Pl. (Adanson) 2: 157 (1763)

The genus is named by Linnaeus in honor of Adam Lonitzer, Latinized as Lonicerus (1528 – 1586), a German mathematician, physician, and botanist, professor of mathematics at the University of Marburg, and author of a treatise on medicinal herbs [5, 6].

2.63 *Ludwigia*

Ludwigia L., Sp. Pl. [Linnaeus] 1: 118 [1204] (1753)

Ludwigia DC., Prodr. [A. P. de Candolle] 3: 58 (1828) nom. illeg.

The genus is named after Christian Gottlieb Ludwig (1709 – 1773), a German physician, botanist, participant in an African expedition, and professor of medicine at Leipzig, correspondent of Linnaeus.

Linnaeus named the genus *Ludwigia* in his honor [5].

2.64 *Mahonia*

Mahonia Nutt., Gen. N. Amer. Pl. [Nuttall]. 1: 211 (-212) (1818), nom. cons.

Mahonia [infragen.unranked] Horridae Fedde, Bot. Jahrb. Syst. 31: 70 (1901)

The genus is dedicated to Bernard McMahon (c. 1775 – 1816), an Irish-origin horticulturist who emigrated to North America, living in Philadelphia, author of "The American gardener's calendar" (1806) [5, 6].

2.65 Malabaila

Malabaila Tausch, Flora 17(1): 356 (1834), nom. illeg.

Malabaila Hoffm., Gen. Pl. Umbell. 125 (1814)

The genus is named for Emmanuel Canal (Joseph Emmanuel Malabayla von Canal) (1745 – 1826), a Bohemian philanthropist, botanist, and agricultural reformer, an honorary citizen of Prague. He founded a botanical school in Prague and a botanical garden called "Canal Garden" [5].

2.66 Malcolmia

Malcolmia W. T. Aiton, Hort. Kew., ed. 2 [W.T.Aiton] 4: 121 (1812), nom. et orth. cons.

The genus could be dedicated to William Malcolm (? – 1798), an English gardener and nurseryman, publisher of "A catalog of hot-house and green-house plants"(1771), or to his son William Malcolm Jr. (1769 – 1835) who continued nursery business. Since the name of the genus was established in 1812, it is possible that it was given in honor of the two aforementioned Malcolm [5].

2.67 Maresia

Maresia Pomel, Nouv. Mat. Fl. Atl. 228 (1874)

The genus is named after Paul Marès (1826 – 1900), a French botanist, a participant in expeditions to Tunisia and Algeria, and a researcher of the Balearic islands' flora. Author of "Flora of the Balearics" [6].

2.68 Marsilea

Marsilea L., Sp. Pl. 2: 1099 (1753)

The genus is dedicated to Luigi Ferdinando Marsili (or Marsigli), Latinized as Marsilius (1658 – 1730), an eminent Italian scientist, botanist and mycologist, author of numerous works, a Fellow of the Royal Society of London and of Montpellier, founder of the Institute of Sciences and Arts of Bologna [6].

2.69 Matthiola

Matthiola L., Genera Plantarum ed. 5 (1754)

Matthiola W.T.Aiton, Hort. Kew., ed. 2 [W.T. Aiton] 4: 119 (1812), nom. et orth. cons.

Matthiola L., Sp. Pl. 2: 1192 (1753)

The genus is named for Pietro Andrea Mattioli, Latinized as Petrus Andreas Matthiolus (1500 – 1577), an Italian physician, naturalist, and botanist from Siena, author of one of the first botanical works of the Modern Age – "Compendium de plantis omnibus" (1571) as well as a translator of Dioscorides [5].

2.70 Middendorfia

Middendorfia Trautv., Mém. Acad. Imp. Sci. St.-Pétersbourg Divers Savans iv. (1842) 489

The genus is dedicated to Alexander Theodor von Middendorff (1815 – 1894), a German-Russian zoologist and botanist, explorer in Lapland and Siberia, as well as the Barents Sea, and professor of zoology at Kyiv University [5].

2.71 Minuartia

Minuartia Loefl., Genera Plantarum ed. 5 (1754)

Minuartia Loefl., Sp. Pl. 1: 89 (1753)

The genus is named after Juan Minuart (1693 – 1768), a Catalan pharmacist and botanist of Barcelona, professor at the Royal Madrid Botanical Garden, where he teaches botany [5].

2.72 **Moehringia**

Moehringia L., Sp. Pl. 1: 359 (1753)

The genus is dedicated by Linnaeus to Paul Heinrich Gerhard Möhring (1710 – 1792), a German physician, naturalist, and botanist, author of "Avium genera" (1752) [5].

2.73 **Moenchia**

Moenchia Roth., Tent. Fl. Germ. 1: 273 (1788)

Moenchia Medik., in Act. Acad. Palat. vi Phys. (1790) 493

Moenchia Ehrh., Neues Mag. Aerzte 5(3): 203 (-204) (1783)

Moenchia Ehrh., Beitr., Naturk. [Ehrhart] ii. 177 (1788)

The genus is dedicated to Conrad Moench (1744 – 1805), a German botanist, professor of botany at Marburg University and author of "Methodus plantarum horti botanici et agri Marburgensis" (1794) [5].

2.74 **Molinia**

Molinia Schrank, Baier. Fl. i. 100, 334 (1789). (1789)

The genus is named after Juan Ignacio Molina, also known as Abate Molina or Giovanni Ignazio Molina (1740 – 1829), a Chilean cleric historian, naturalist and botanist, professor at the University of Bologna, author of "Saggio sulla storia naturale del Chili" (1782) [5, 6].

2.75 **Montia**

Montia L., Genera Plantarum ed. 5 (1754)

Montia L., Sp. Pl. 1: 87 (1753)

Montia Mill., Gard. Dict. Abr., ed. 4. (1754); vide Dandy, Ind. Gen. Vasc. Pl. 1753-74(Regn. Veg. 51) 65 (1967), non L. (1754)

The genus is named after Giuseppe Monti (1682 – 1760), an Italian chemist and botanist, professor of botany and director of the Bologna Botanical Garden [5]. Carl Linnaeus published *Montia* in his honor.

2.76 **Morina**

Morina L., Sp. Pl. 1: 28 (1753)

The genus is named for Louis Pierre Morin (1635 – 1715), a French physician and botanist, elected associate botanist at the Royal Academy of Sciences in Paris in 1699 [5, 7].

2.77 **Neslia**

Neslia Desv., J. Bot. Agric. 3: 162 (1815)

The genus is dedicated to Jacques Amable Nicolas de Nesle (1735 – 1819), a French pharmacist and gardener, director of the botanical garden at Poitiers, and author of "Petite introduction à la botanique" [5].

2.78 **Nonea**

Nonea Medik., Philos. Bot. (Medikus) 1: 31 (1789)

The genus is named after Johann Philipp Nonne (1729 – 1772), a German physician and botanist, professor at Erfurt, and author of "Flora in territorio Erfordensi indigena" (1763) [5].

2.79 **Orlaya**

Orlaya Hoffm., Gen. Pl. Umbell. 58 (1814)

The genus is dedicated to Johann Orlay (1770 – 1827), a Hungarian physician and botanist, secretary of the Academy of Sciences in St. Petersburg [5, 6].

2.80 **Parentucellia**

Parentucellia Viv., Fl. Libyc. Spec. 31 (1824)

Parentucellia Viv., Fl. Libyc. Spec. 31. t. 21. f. 3 (1824) (1824)

The genus is dedicated to Tommaso Parentucelli (1398 – 1455) who became pope in 1447 with the name of Nicolò V, patron and humanist, founder of the Apostolic Library, and the Botanical Garden in the Vatican [5, 7].

2.81 **Petrosimonia**

Petrosimonia Bunge, Anabas. Rev. 52 (1862)

The genus is dedicated to Peter (Pyotr) Simon von Pallas (1741 – 1811), a Prussian biologist, botanist, and zoologist, professor at the St Petersburg Academy of Sciences, famous for his explorations in Russia [6].

2.82 **Pritzelago**

Pritzelago Kuntze, Revis. Gen. Pl. 1: 35 (1891)

The genus is dedicated to Georg August Pritzel (1815 – 1874), a German librarian and botanist, archivist at the Prussian Academy of Sciences [6]. The name is formed through suffix *-ago* denoting connection, likeness, or some effect produced by the plant or by natural quality inherent in this plant [9].

2.83 **Puccinellia**

Puccinellia Parl., Fl. Ital. (Parlatore) 1: 366 (1848)

The genus is dedicated to Benedetto Luigi Puccinelli (1808 – 1850), an Italian botanist and explorer, professor of botany, director of the botanical garden in Lucca, and author of a "Flora di Lucca" and a "Synopsis Plantarum in Agro Lucensi Sponte Nascentium" (1841) [6].

2.84 **Queria**

Queria Loefl., Sp. Pl. 1: 90 (1753)

The genus is named after José Quer y Martínez (1695 – 1764), a Spanish military surgeon, interested in botany, and keen plant collector, participated in the foundation of the Royal Madrid Botanical Garden, author of the first four volumes of "Flora española ó Historia de las plantas que se crían en España" [5].

2.85 **Ramonda**

Ramonda Caruel, Epit. Fl. Eur. ii. (1894) 140

Ramonda Rich., Syn. Pl. [Persoon] 1: 216 (1805), nom. cons.

The genus is named for Louis-François Èlisabeth Ramond, baron de Carbonnières (1753 – 1827), a French politician, botanist and geologist, member of the French Academy of Sciences, and explorer of the high areas of the Pyrenees where this species grows [6].

2.86 **Reichardia**

Reichardia Roth, Bot. Abh. Beobacht. 35 (1787)

Reichardia Roth, Nov. Pl. Sp. 210 (1821) nom. illeg.

Reichardia Dennst., Schlüssel Hortus Malab. 32 (1818) (1818)

Reichardia Roth, Catal. Bot. 2: 64 (1800), nom. illeg.

The genus is dedicated to Johann Jacob (Jakob) Reichard (1743 – 1782), a German physician and botanist of Frankfurt. He was in charge of the library and botanical garden of Senckenberg Foundation while working as a chief physician there. Author of "Enumeratio stirpi horti botanici senckenbergiani" (1782), and editor of Linnaeus' "Systema Plantarum" (1779) [5].

2.87 Rindera

Rindera Pall., Reise Russ. Reich. 1: 486 (1771)

The genus name is dedicated by Peter (Pyotr) Simon von Pallas to Franz Andreas Rinder (translated into Russian as Andrei Andreevich, 1714 – 1771), a German-born Russian physician working in Orenburg and Moscow, dean of medicine in Moscow. Rinder discovered the plant *Rindera* in the Ural mountains and was the first to describe it [5, 6].

2.88 Robinia

Robinia L., Sp. Pl. 2: 722 (1753)

Robinia L., Genera Plantarum ed. 5 (1754)

Linnaeus dedicates the genus to Jean Robin (1550 – 1629) and his son Vespasian (1579 – 1662), French botanists, gardeners, and herbalists at the French royal court who introduced *Robinia pseudoacacia* to Europe [6].

2.89 Rochelia

Rochelia Rchb., Flora 7: 243 (1824)

Rochelia Roem. & Schut., Syst. Veg., ed. 15 bis [Roemer & Schultes] 4: p. xi, 108 (1819)

The genus is dedicated to Anton Rochel (1770 – 1847), an Austro-Hungarian surgeon and botanist, curator of the Botanical Garden in Pest, and explorer of flora in Banat and Carpathians [5].

2.90 Roemeria

Roemeria Moench, Methodus (Moench) 341 (1794) (1794)

Roemeria Dennst., Schlüssel Hortus Malab. 30 (1818) (1818)

Roemeria Zea ex Roem. & Schult., Syst. Veg. ed. 15 bis [Roemer & Schultes] 1: 61, 287 (1817)

Roemeria Thunb., Nov. Gen. Pl. [Thunberg] 9: 130, genus spurium (1798)

Roemeria Medik., Ann. Bot. (Usteri) 3: 15; DC. Syst. ii. 92 (1821) (1792)

The genus is named after Johann Jacob Roemer (1763 – 1819), a Swiss physician, entomologist, botanist, professor of botany in Zurich, and a foreign member of the Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences. [6].

2.91 Ruppia

Ruppia L., Genera Plantarum ed. 5 (1754)

Ruppia L., Sp. Pl. 1: 127 (1753)

Ruppia L., Sp. Pl. [Linnaeus] 1: 127 (1753)

Linnaeus gave the name in honor of Heinrich Bernhard Rupp, Latinized as Ruppium (1688 – 1719), a German botanist of Jena, author of "Flora Jenensis" (1718) [5].

2.92 *Salvinia*

Salvinia P.Micheli ex Adans., Fam. Pl. (Adanson) 2: 15 (1763), isonym.

Salvinia Guett., Hist. Acad. Roy. Sci. Mém. Math. Phys. (Paris, 4to) 1762(2): 546 (1762), nom. inval.

Salvinia Ség., Pl. Veron. 3: 52 (-53) (1754)

The genus is dedicated to Antonio Maria Salvini (1653 – 1729), an Italian scholar and eminent translator of ancient languages texts, professor of Greek language at Florentine Academy. The name *Salvinia* is given by his friend Pier Antonio Micheli (1679 – 1737), illustrious Florentine botanist and mycologist [5].

2.93 *Saussurea*

Saussurea Salisb., Trans. Linn. Soc. London 8: 11 (1807)

Saussurea DC., Ann. Mus. Natl. Hist. Nat. 16: 156, 198, tt. 10, 13 (1810), nom. cons.

The genus is named after Horace Bénédict de Saussure (1740 – 1799), a Swiss meteorologist, pioneer of mountaineering, geologist, and naturalist; a foreign member of the Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences, the Royal Society of London, and l'Académie des sciences de Paris; and also, after his son Nicolas-Théodore de Saussure (1767 – 1845), chemist and plant physiologist, researcher of the photosynthesis process, author of "Récherches chimiques sur la Végétation" (1804) [5, 6].

2.94 *Schivereckia*

Schivereckia Andr. ex DC., Syst. Nat. [Candolle] 2: 300 (1821)

The genus is dedicated to Swibert (Suibert) Burkhart Schivereck (1742 – 1806), an Austrian botanist, professor of botany at the University of Innsbruck, later transferred to the University of Lemberg (today Lviv in Ukraine), and being the first professor of chemistry and botany there [5, 7].

2.95 *Sesleria*

Sesleria Scop., Fl. Carniol. 63 (1760)

Sesleria Nutt., Gen. N. Amer. Pl. [Nuttall]. 1: 64 (1818)

The genus is dedicated to Leonardo Sesler (1683– 1785), an Italian physician, naturalist, and botanist, owner of a private botanical garden in Padua [5, 6].

2.96 *Sherardia*

Sherardia Boehm., Def. Gen. Pl., ed. 3. 408; vide Dandy, Ind. Gen. Vasc. Pl. 1753-74 (Regn. Veg. 51) 81 (1967), non L. & non Mill. (1760)

Sherardia L., Genera Plantarum ed. 5 (1754)

Sherardia L., Sp. Pl. 1: 102 (1753)

The genus is named after William Sherard (1659 – 1728), an English diplomat, botanist, and plant collector, patron of several botanists as J. J. Dilenius, P. A. Micheli, and others, a pupil of Tournefort, and a friend and pupil of Paul Hermann in Leyden [5, 6].

2.97 *Sibbaldia*

Sibbaldia L., Sp. Pl. 1: 284 (1753)

The genus is dedicated to Robert Sibbald (1641 – 1722), a Scottish physician and naturalist, antiquary, and professor of medicine at the University of Edinburgh, author of "Scotia illustrata" (1684). In 1667 he started the Edinburgh botanical garden [5, 7].

2.98 *Sieglingia*

Sieglingia Bernh., Syst. Verz. (Bernhardi) 20, 44 (1800), nom. rej.

The genus is named after Johann Blasius Siegling (1760 – 1835), a German botanist, professor of mathematics and philosophy at Erfurt, and an explorer of the local flora [6, 8].

2.99 *Stefanoffia*

Stefanoffia H. Wolff, Notizbl. Bot. Gart. Berlin-Dahlem 9: 282 (1925)

The name is given in honor of Boris Stefanoff (1894 – 1979), a Bulgarian botanist and dendrologist, one of the founders of this discipline in Bulgaria, curator at the herbarium of Sofia University, and a member of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences from 1948, author of several basic works [8].

2.100 *Sternbergia*

Sternbergia Waldst. & Kit., Descr. Icon. Pl. Hung. 2: 172 (1804)

The genus is dedicated to Caspar (Kaspar) Maria von Sternberg (1761 – 1838), a Bohemian theologian, naturalist, and botanist believed to be the founder of modern paleobotany, established the Bohemian National Museum in Prague. He also established a botanical garden in Regensburg as well as in Radnice, Bohemia, and conducted paleobotanical research there [5, 6].

2.101 *Swertia*

Swertia All., Fl. Pedem. i. 208 (1785) (1785)

Swertia Boehm., Def. Gen. Pl., ed. 3. 171; vide Dandy, Ind. Gen. Vasc. Pl. 1753-74 (Regn. Veg. 51) 84 (1967), non L. (1760)

Swertia L., Genera Plantarum ed. 5 (1754)

Swertia L., Sp. Pl. 1: 226 (1753)

The genus is dedicated to Emanuel Swert (1552 – 1612), a Dutch gardener, florist, and author of "Florilegium" (1612) [5].

2.102 *Teesdalia*

Teesdalia W. T. Aiton, Hort. Kew., ed. 2 [W.T. Aiton] 4: 83 (1812), nom. illeg.

The genus is named after Robert Teesdale (1740 – 1804), an English botanist and horticulturist in Yorkshire, a member of the Linnean Society of London, and author of "Plantae Eboracenses" (1792) [5].

2.103 *Telekia*

Telekia Baumg., Enum. Stirp. Transsilv. 3: 149 (1817)

The genus is dedicated to Count Sámuel Teleki de Szék (1739 – 1822), a Hungarian nobleman, chancellor of the Habsburgs for Transylvania, patron of sciences and arts, book collector, and founder of the Teleki Library in Târgu Mureș, Transylvania [5, 6].

2.104 *Tozzia*

Tozzia L., Sp. Pl. 2: 607 (1753)

The genus is named after Don Bruno Tozzi (1656 – 1743), abbot of Vallombrosa, botanist, and plant collector, by his pupil Pier Antonio Micheli [6].

2.105 *Traunsteinera*

Traunsteinera Rchb., Deut. Bot. Herb.-Buch 50. 1841; Fl. Sax. 87. 1844

The genus is dedicated to Joseph Traunsteiner (1798 – 1850), an Austrian botanist and pharmacist in Kitzbühel, explorer of Tyrolean flora [5, 6].

2.106 *Trinia*

Trinia Hoffm., Gen. Pl. Umbell. xxix, 92 (1814)

The genus is dedicated to Carl Bernhard von Trinius (1778 – 1844), a German-born physician and botanist, interested in grasses, working both in Germany and Russia, in St. Petersburg, and author of "Species graminum, iconibus et descriptionibus illustravit" (1828 – 1936) [5, 8].

2.107 *Turgenia*

Turgenia Hoffm., Gen. Pl. Umbell. 59 (1814)

The genus is dedicated to Alexander Ivanovich Turgenev (1784 – 1845), a Russian historian and secretary of state in the Russian tsarist administration. In 1841 – 1842, he published the two-volume work "Historica Russiae Monumenta ex antiquis exterarum gentium archivis et bibliothecis deprompta ab A. I. Turgenevio" [5, 6].

2.108 *Turgeniopsis*

Turgeniopsis Boiss., Ann. Sci. Nat., Bot. sér. 3, 2: 53 (1844)

The genus name derives from *Turgenia* (see 2.107.) combined with the stem of Greek origin *ὄψις* (view), thereby indicating similarity with the genus *Turgenia*.

2.109 *Vallisneria*

Vallisneria L., Genera Plantarum ed. 5 (1754)

Vallisneria L., Sp. Pl. 2: 1015 (1753)

The genus is named after Antonio Vallisneri (or Vallisnieri, 1661 – 1730), an Italian physician, naturalist, and botanist, a pupil of Marcello Malpighi; professor of medicine at the University of Padua, member of the Royal Society of London. He is considered one of the greatest exponents of the Galilean school of experimental scientists between the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries, with studies covering a wide range of different scientific branches [6].

2.110 *Velezia*

Velezia L., Sp. Pl. 1: 332 (1753)

Carl Linnaeus named this genus after Cristóbal Velèz (c. 1710 – 1753), a Spanish pharmacist and botanist, a pupil of Minuart, and secretary of the College of Pharmacists in Madrid, friend and collaborator of Pehr Löfving during his Spanish stay, correspondent of Linnaeus. His research on Madrid flora was unfinished due to his premature death [5, 6].

2.111 *Ventenata*

Ventenata Koeler, Descr. Gram. [Koeler] 272 (1802)

The genus is dedicated to Étienne Pierre Ventenat (1757 – 1808), a French librarian and botanist, worked for Empress Joséphine de Beauharnais at the Château de Malmaison, author of several botanical works [5, 6].

2.112 *Vulpia*

Vulpia C. C. Gmel., Fl. Bad. 1: 8 (1805)

The genus is named after Johann Samuel Vulpius (1760 – 1846), a German botanist and pharmacist in Pforzheim, an excellent florist [5, 6].

2.113 *Waldsteinia*

Waldsteinia Willd., Neue Schriften Ges. Naturf. Freunde Berlin 2: 105 (1799)

The genus is dedicated to Count Franz de Paula Adam Norbert Wenzel Ludwig Valentin von Waldstein-Wartenberg (1759 – 1823), a soldier of the army of the Austro-Hungarian Empire, botanist, and naturalist who studied the Hungarian flora together with Pál Kitaibel and both together wrote "Descriptiones et icones plantarum rariorum Hungariae" (1802 – 1812) [5, 6].

2.114 *Wolffia*

Wolffia Horkel ex Schleid., *Linnaea* 13(4): 389 (1839)

Wolffia Horkel ex Schleid., *Beitr. Bot. [Schleiden]* 1: 233 (1844), nom. cons.

The genus is dedicated to Johann Friedrich Wolff (1778 – 1806), a German physician, botanist, entomologist, and illustrator who wrote and illustrated a study on the *Lemna* genus: "Commentatio de Lemna" (1801) [5, 6].

2.115 *Zannichellia*

Zannichellia L., *Genera Plantarum* ed. 5 (1754)

Zannichellia L., *Sp. Pl. [Linnaeus]* 2: 969 (1753)

The genus is dedicated to Giovanni Gerolamo Zannichelli (1662 – 1729), a Venetian physician, chemist, pharmacist, and keen botanist of Modenese origin, author of an illustrated work on the flora of the Lidi Veneti: "Istoria delle piante che nascono ne' lidi intorno a Venezia" (1735) [5, 6].

3. The grammatical form of the genera names – rules and exceptions

The genus names are nouns feminine, whether they note a man or a woman (ICBN, Recommendation 20A) [3]. When forming these names, several word-formative rules should be considered (ICBN, Recommendation 60B) [3]:

3.1 When the name of the person ends with a vowel, the letter -a is added (e. g. *Duchesnea* – from A.N. Duchesne, or *Berteroa* – for C. L. G. Bertero). Exceptions: when the name ends with -a, -ea is added; when with -ea, no letter is added

Deviations from this recommendation were identified at the following names:

- *Blackstonia* instead of *Blackstonea* (from J. Blackstone)
- *Cortusa* instead of *Cortusoa* (from G. A. Cortuso)
- *Danthonia* instead of *Danthoinea* (from E. Danthoine)
- *Galilea* instead of *Galileia* (from G. Galilei)
- *Galinsoga* instead of *Galinsogaea* (from I. M. M. de Galinsoga)
- *Imperata* instead of *Imperatoa* (from F. Imperato)
- *Malabaila* instead of *Malabailaea* (from J. E. Malabayla)
- *Marsilea* instead of *Marsilia* (from L. F. Marsili)
- *Matthiola* instead of *Matthiolia* (from P. A. Matthioli)
- *Molina* instead of *Molinaea* (from J. I. Molina)
- *Neslia* instead of *Neslea* (from J. A. N. de Nesle)
- *Teesdalia* instead of *Teesdalea* (from R. Teesdale)

3.2 When the name of the person ends with a consonant, the letters -ia are added (e. g. *Ammannia* – from P. Ammann, or *Reichardia* – from J. J. Reichard) but when the name ends with -er, both -ia and -a is appropriate (e. g. *Sesleria* – from Sesler and *Listera* – from Lister).

Deviations:

- *Commelina* instead of *Commelinia* (from J. Commelin)
- *Morina* instead of *Morinia* (from L. P. Morin)
- *Ramonda* instead of *Ramondia* (from L.-F. Ramond)
- *Ventenata* instead of *Ventenatia* (from É. P. Ventenat)

3.3 In Latinized personal names ending with -us, this ending is dropped (e. g. *Ruppia* – from *Ruppius*) before applying the previous rules.

We should note one more feature: there is sometimes a discrepancy between the spelling of the name of the eponym in the corresponding national language and the Latinized generic name based on it – e. g. *Gleditsia* from Latinized variant *Gleditsius* of J. G. Gleditsch, or *Danthonia* from the French É. Danthoine.

3.4 There also exist generic names derived from personal names through different affixes. Such an option is foreseen in ICBN, Recommendation 60B, Note 2 [3]: More than one generic name, or epithet of a subdivision of a genus, may be based on the same personal name, e. g. by adding a prefix or suffix to that personal name or by using an anagram or abbreviation of it. We find this word-formation pattern in the following generic names:

3.4.1 *Bellardiochloa*

From *Bellardia* and the stem of Greek origin *χλόα* (grass) hence a herbaceous plant named after the Italian botanist C. Bellardi;

3.4.2 *Dantoniastrum*

From *Danthonia* and the suffix *-astrum* meaning resemblance hence a plant genus resembling *Danthonia*;

3.4.3 *Gentianella*

From *Gentiana* and the diminutive suffix *-ella* hence small gentian.

3.4.4 *Pritzelago*

From *Pritzel* (a German botanist) and the suffix *-ago* with which derivative nouns with various meanings are formed.

3.4.5 *Turgeniopsis*

From *Turgenia* and the stem of Greek origin *ὄψις* (view), which means resemblance, likeness hence a plant similar to *Turgenia*. One more peculiarity regarding this name: it should be *Turgenevia* because the name that it derived from is Turgenev.

4. Conclusion

The research on the genera names dedicated to ingenuine persons (eponyms) is a small step in the acquaintance of the various and multi-layered botanical denominations. These names do not carry direct information about the characteristic features and peculiarities of the described genus, but in a special way, they enrich the cultural context in which this genus arose. Getting to know the history, life path, and achievements of significant individuals from different eras expands the horizon of knowledge and can be an inspiring stimulus for the searching human spirit.

Regarding the grammar form of the eponymic names, there exist several deviations from the nomenclature recommendations, and they probably could be interpreted as an effort to simplify and make it easier to perceive the newly created generic names.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The work is an independent development of the author, with no supporting grants or competing interests.

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